

1 **Reporting Quality of Systematic Review Protocols in Environmental and**
2 **Occupational Toxicology: A meta-epidemiology study**

3

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31 **Abstract**

32 **Background:** Systematic reviews (SR) are increasingly used in toxicology to inform
33 regulatory decisions and research prioritization. SR protocols (SRP), which outline
34 planned methods in advance, are essential for ensuring transparency and
35 reproducibility. However, little is known about the extent and reporting quality of peer-
36 reviewed protocols ~~s-reporting~~ in environmental and occupational toxicology.

37 **Objective:** To assess publishing trends, characteristics, and reporting quality of SRP
38 published in peer-reviewed journals within the fields of environmental and occupational
39 toxicology.

40 **Methods:** We searched four databases (PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, EMBASE)
41 using predefined search strings to identify peer-reviewed SRP examining the health
42 effects of environmental or occupational exposures. Deduplication was performed in R.
43 Protocols were screened independently by two reviewers using eligibility criteria based
44 on the Population - Concept - Context (PCC) framework. Data extraction included
45 bibliographic details, exposures, outcomes, evidence streams, and use of reporting
46 checklists. Descriptive statistics were used to analyze publication trends and protocol
47 characteristics. Reporting quality was assessed using a 15-item PRISMA-P-based tool,
48 eleven of which were used to assess reporting quality.

49 **Results:** We identified 3,787 records and included 37 peer-reviewed SRPs. These
50 protocols were published between 2014 and 2024, with a peak in 2021. Most protocols
51 focused on environmental toxicology (65%). Academic institutions served as the primary
52 affiliations (76%), and most protocols targeted human evidence (78%). Air pollutants
53 were the most common exposures, and the most frequently studied outcomes involved
54 the nervous, respiratory, and female reproductive systems. Twenty-nine protocols (78%)
55 mentioned using a reporting guideline, mostly PRISMA-P. All studies reported funding
56 sources, but only 32% described the funder's role. Twelve (%) protocols met all 11
57 minimal reporting quality criteria. Protocols most often underreport data management
58 procedures (2754%), confidence in cumulative evidence (73%), and data
59 collection/extraction processes (763%). In contrast, more than 90% of protocols reported
60 review rationale, information sources, and study selection process.

61

62 **Conclusions:** A limited number of peer-reviewed protocols have been published in
63 environmental and occupational toxicology. In general, the peer-reviewed protocols
64 address the minimum reporting requirements. Further research is needed to evaluate
65 methodological quality in greater detail, how closely systematic reviews adhere to their
66 pre-published protocols, and to expand the assessment to SRP published in the grey
67 literature.

68 **Keywords:** systematic review protocols, toxicology, evidence-based toxicology,
69 reporting quality

70 **Registration:** 10.5281/zenodo.18187257

71 **1. Background**

72 Systematic reviews (SRs), an evidence-based toxicology tool, are increasingly used to
73 systematically identify, evaluate, and synthesize the available evidence addressing
74 specific toxicological questions (Hartung & Tsaioun, 2024; Senerth et al., 2024; Woodruff
75 & Sutton, 2014). By integrating findings across multiple studies, SRs support regulatory
76 decision-making, identify knowledge gaps, guide future research priorities, and inform
77 the efficient allocation of research resources (Farhat et al., 2022; Hoffmann et al., 2017;
78 Wikoff & Fitch, 2024)

79 A key component of SR workflows is the development of a systematic review protocol
80 (SRP) that outlines the research plans and describes the methods to be applied before
81 the review (Moher et al., 2009; Senerth et al., 2024). SRPs are crucial for minimizing
82 duplication of research (Moher, 2013; Siontis et al., 2013), facilitating proactive planning
83 and anticipation of potential challenges, ensuring methodological validity, enabling
84 replication of the review when necessary, and preventing arbitrary decision-making
85 (Andrade et al., 2019; Du et al., 2022; Hardwicke & Wagenmakers, 2023; Shamseer et
86 al., 2015; Stewart et al., 2012; K. van der Braak et al., 2023).

87 Public availability of protocols is considered a major indicator of SR methodological
88 quality, according to A Measurement Tool to Assess Systematic Reviews (AMSTAR-2)
89 (Shea et al., 2017). SR protocols (SRPs) are typically made publicly available either
90 through registration on online platforms (e.g., Zenodo, OSF, Figshare, PROSPERO,
91 protocols.io) or as peer-reviewed publication in scientific journals (Pieper & Rombey,
92 2022). Compared to peer-reviewed protocols, the advantage of registered protocols is

93 rapid, free public dissemination (Andrade et al., 2019). However, the lack of global
94 searchability and the absence of peer-review evaluation are the main drawbacks of
95 protocols available on online registration platforms (Schiavo, 2019; Tawfik et al., 2020;
96 Kim Van Der Braak et al., 2023)

97 Despite recognition of the importance of publicly available SRPs, this step is frequently
98 omitted in the SR process (Kusala Pussegoda et al., 2017). Previous studies show that
99 only a small proportion of SRs report protocol information, with some as low as 6% (102
100 / 1741) (Kusala Pussegoda et al., 2017; K. van der Braak et al., 2023). Most are
101 registered in PROSPERO, which does not include traditional journal-style peer review
102 (Andrade et al., 2019; Van Der Braak et al., 2022). Another study conducted by Menon
103 et al. (2022) analyzed the methodological quality of a limited sample of SRs in
104 environmental health and revealed that only 17% of the reviewed SRs had identifiable
105 SRP, all registered in PROSPERO (Menon et al., 2022). Similarly, ten years ago, less
106 than 10% of reviews in environmental epidemiology reported a registered or published
107 protocol (Sheehan & Lam, 2015).

108 Because the quality of SRPs in environmental and occupational toxicology remains
109 poorly characterized, we assessed their reporting quality following our previously
110 published protocol (Pavlovic et al., 2025). Following our previously published protocol,
111 we predefined the search strategy, study selection, data extraction, and analysis.
112 Reporting quality was operationalized as completeness of reporting, measured by
113 adherence to essential elements derived from the PRISMA-P checklist (Shamseer et al.,
114 2015). Systematic Reviews (SR) are increasingly used in toxicology to synthesize
115 evidence, for example, to summarize the available studies on a toxicological question (or
116 issue), support regulatory decision-making, map knowledge gaps, and allocate research
117 resources (Farhat et al., 2022; Hoffmann et al., 2017; National Academies of Sciences &
118 National Academies of Sciences, 2023)

119 An important component of SR workflows is the use of a protocol that outlines the
120 research plans and describes the methods to be applied before the review (Peters et al.,
121 2020; Senearth et al., 2024). Review protocols are crucial for minimizing duplication of
122 research, facilitating proactive planning and anticipation of potential challenges, ensuring
123 methodological validity, enabling replication of the review when necessary, and
124 preventing arbitrary decision-making (Pussegoda et al., 2017). As such, the public
125 availability of protocols is one of the critical domains of methodological quality of an SR,

126 according to A Measurement Tool to Assess Systematic Reviews (AMSTAR-2) (Shea
127 et al., 2017). It has been shown that public protocols can reduce the risk of bias, for
128 instance, from selective reporting, increase reproducibility, enable validity judgment, and
129 increase the overall scientific rigor of conducted research (Shamseer et al., 2015).

130 SR protocols (SRP) are usually made publicly available via two mechanisms: registration
131 on online platforms (e.g., Zenodo, OSF, Figshare, PROSPERO, protocols.io) or
132 publishing as peer-reviewed publications in scientific journals (Pieper & Rombey, 2022).
133 Compared to peer-reviewed protocols, the advantage of registered protocols is rapid and
134 free-of-charge release and access. However, the lack of global searchability and the
135 absence of peer-review evaluation are the main drawbacks of protocols available on
136 online registration platforms (Schiavo, 2019).

137 Despite recognition of the importance of SRP registering/publishing, this step is
138 frequently omitted in the SR process (Moher et al., 2009). Previous studies showed that
139 only 38% (136/357) of SR related to healthcare interventions had pre-registered SRP,
140 with most registered in PROSPERO, a platform with limited peer review options (Van
141 Der Braak et al., 2022). Another study conducted by Menon et al. (2022) analyzed the
142 methodological quality of a limited sample of SR in environmental health and revealed
143 that only 17% of the reviewed SR had identifiable SRP, all registered also in
144 PROSPERO (Menon et al., 2022). Similarly, ten years ago, less than 10% of reviews in
145 environmental epidemiology reported a pre-registered/published protocol (Sheehan &
146 Lam, 2015).

147 Another emerging concern is related to the methodological and reporting quality of SR.
148 Poorly developed and reported SR are prone to bias, can lead to misleading
149 conclusions, and have diminished applicability (Pussegoda et al., 2017). The lack of
150 protocols and the compromised reporting quality of SRP are potentially important
151 contributors to this problem (Frost et al., 2022).

152 As the extent of this issue in environmental and occupational toxicology is poorly
153 understood, we assessed the reporting quality of SRP in this domain following the
154 previously published protocol (Pavlovic et al., 2025). The protocol predefined the search,
155 selection, data extraction, and analysis. To operationalize the data analysis, we defined
156 reporting quality as the completeness of reporting assessed by the adherence to
157 essential elements derived from the PRISMA-P checklist (Shamseer et al., 2015).

158

159 **Objective**

160 The objective of this meta-epidemiological study was to assess the reporting quality of
161 protocols that evaluate the health effects of exposures in environmental and
162 occupational toxicology, which were published in peer-reviewed journals.

163

164 In line with our objective, we have three research questions:

165

- 166 1. What is the number and yearly distribution of environmental and occupational
167 toxicology protocols published in peer-reviewed journals?
- 168 2. What are the characteristics (bibliographical data, evidence types, field of study,
169 and guidelines/checklists used for developing the protocol) of those protocols?
- 170 3. What is the reporting quality of the protocols?

171 **2. Methods**

172 This study followed established reporting guidelines for meta-epidemiology research
173 (Murad & Wang, 2017). Detailed methodology was reported in the previously published
174 protocol (Pavlovic et al., 2025) and registered on Zenodo (10.5281/zenodo.14269983).
175 This study was reported following the PRISMA-A (2020), PRISMA-S (2020), and the
176 adapted PRISMA reporting checklist developed for meta-epidemiology studies (Murad &
177 Wang, 2017; Page et al., 2021; Rethlefsen et al., 2021). Filled checklists are available in
178 Supplementary Material, in the Appendices A.1, A.2, and A.3, respectively.

179 **2.1 Eligibility Criteria**

180 We used the Population - Concept - Context (PCC) framework (see *Table 1*), as per
181 the methodological guide (Peters et al., 2020), to structure the eligibility criteria, following
182 the published protocol (Pavlovic et al., 2025).

183

184 **Table 1.** *Eligibility Criteria are presented using the PCC framework.*

PCC	Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
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Population	Systematic Review Protocols (SRP), meta-analysis protocols that self-identified as such in their title	Protocols for other types of reviews, such as umbrella reviews - e.g., protocol of a Systematic Review of SR or meta-analyses Scoping Review Protocols Methodological and experimental protocols
Concept	Assessment of health effects of chemicals or chemical mixtures due to exposures OR Assessment of associations between exposures to chemical or chemical mixtures and health effects.	Assessment of health effects of chemicals or chemical mixtures due to <u>intentional</u> exposures OR Assessment of exposures only OR Aiming to mitigate, remediate, or prevent exposures/effects of exposures
Context	Occupational or environmental toxicology	Other fields of toxicology: safety pharmacology, toxicology of compounds, mixtures (chemical, biological), or extracts/preparations (e.g., herbal medicine) intended to prevent, treat, and diagnose diseases (drugs) or medical devices for human or animal use (veterinary drugs); toxicology of biological and physical hazards; forensic toxicology; analytical toxicology; clinical toxicology; ecotoxicology; toxicology of psychoactive controlled substances.
Types of evidence source	Peer-reviewed journal articles	Abstracts from conferences Gray literature (e.g., PROSPERO protocols)

185

186

187 **2.2 Search and study selection**

188 We followed a pre-validated PRISMA-S compliant search strategy for the four databases
189 PubMed [.com](#), Scopus [.com](#), [Embase.com and Core Collection of the](#) Web of Science
190 [platform](#), ~~and Embase~~ (see Appendices B.1, B.2, and B.3 of the published protocol
191 (Pavlovic et al., 2025). Records published in the English language and those published
192 in languages other than English that can be located by English-language searches were
193 included in our search.

194 Searches were conducted on December 6th, 2024. In executing the search strategy, no
195 limitations or filters were used. Duplicate records were removed in R, using ‘tidyverse’
196 and ‘synthesisr’ packages (Westgate, 2019; Wickham et al., 2019). Following
197 deduplication in R v.4.2.3 (R Core Team, 2023) a library of records was imported into
198 Covidence (*Covidence*, 2024). The code is available on Zenodo:

199 10.5281/zenodo.18187257

200 Title / abstract and full-text screening were conducted in Covidence by four reviewers
201 (MPA, SEH, NVI, GVI) in duplicates. Any disagreements were resolved during the
202 meetings, and if no resolution could be achieved, a third reviewer was consulted. The list
203 of excluded records, as well as included protocols, is available in Appendix B.2 and B.3,
204 respectively.

205

206 **2.3 Data Extraction**

207 Data extraction was conducted by four reviewers (SEH, MPA, GVI, EOM) in duplicate in
208 Covidence. Due to the high sensitivity of the software, even minor differences (e.g.,
209 spaces, capital letters) were flagged, and they were resolved by MPA. For the critical
210 difference (e.g., chemical mixture) discussion meeting was organized, and a third
211 reviewer was advised if the conflict could not be resolved appropriately.

212 The following information was collected related to study characteristics:

- 213 ● General information, including study DOI, title, journal name, first author’s
214 location, and affiliation,
- 215 ● The field of study is categorized as occupational, environmental toxicology, or
216 other.
- 217 ● The evidence streams are categorized as studies involving human subjects,
218 animal studies, new approach methodologies, or others,

- 219 • The exposure to identify the chemicals or chemical mixtures studied (free text),
- 220 • The adverse health outcome(s) specified (free text),
- 221 • The guideline or checklist used, if any.

222 The reporting quality in the context of this study was assessed as adherence to minimal
 223 reporting items based on the PRISMA-P checklist (Shamseer et al., 2015). PRISMA-P
 224 2015 was selected as a well-established reporting checklist for SRP developed primarily
 225 in the context of health care SR. Thus, we modified the PRISMA-P items by excluding,
 226 merging, and rephrasing items using terminology that we expected to be more common
 227 in a toxicological context. Details are specified in Pavlovic et al. 2025, and the modified
 228 PRISMA-P used for assessment is available in Table 2.

229 The items were subdivided into those not directly (A1-A4, e.g., protocol registration) and
 230 directly related to reporting quality (Q1-Q11, e.g., confidence in cumulative evidence).

231 The reporting assessments were conducted in Covidence by two independent assessors
 232 (MPA/SEH). Any disagreement was discussed at the meeting, and if no resolution was
 233 achieved, the third reviewer’s opinion was sought (GVI).

234 **Table 2.** Adapted PRISMA-P 2015 checklist used for assessment of completeness of
 235 reporting for both administrative (A1-A4) and quality-related items (Q1-Q11)

Item	Assessment option and coding (in brackets)
A1. Registration	Reported (1) if the name of the register and a unique document identifier are provided.
	Not reported (0) otherwise
A2. Author contributions	Reported (1) if the contribution of each author is indicated.
	Not reported (0) otherwise
A3. Funder and/or sponsor information*	Reported (1) if funder and/or sponsor information is provided or if it is stated that no funding was received. Minimum data has to include the full name of the funding source and grant number, in case of federal or state funding agencies, foundations, and non-governmental organizations, and/or sponsor name
	Not reported (0) otherwise
A4. Role of funder and/or sponsor	Not applicable (NA) if no funding was received AND no sponsor was indicated.

	Reported (1) if funder and/or sponsor involvement is described.
	Not reported (0) otherwise.
Q1. Rationale	Reported (1) if the topic importance and the necessity of the review are described.
	Not reported (0) otherwise.
Q2. Objectives	Reported (1) if a key element framing, such as (e.g. PECO: population, exposure, comparison, and outcomes) is provided. Note: The information may be provided in a dedicated sub-chapter or in the context of the eligibility criteria.
	Not reported (0) otherwise.
Q3. Eligibility criteria	Reported (1) if criteria related to the individual key elements are reported. For each key element not addressed, a justification is provided.
	Not reported (0) otherwise.
Q4. Information sources	Reported (1) if databases OR other resources (e.g., websites) are stated.
	Not reported (0) otherwise.
Q5. Search strategy	Reported (1) if the search string, incl. limitations, if applicable, for at least one database is provided.
	Not reported (0) otherwise.
Q6. Data management	Reported (1) if the data management software/web-based platform to be used in search, study selection, and data extraction/assessment is indicated
	Not reported (0) otherwise.
Q7. Selection process	Reported (1) if the procedure for inclusion of studies (i.e., number of independent reviewers AND conflict resolution) is stated.
	Not reported (0) otherwise.
Q8. Data collection and extraction process	Reported (1) if the procedure for extracting data (i.e., number of independent reviewers AND conflict resolution) AND a list of all data items expected to be collected is provided.
	Not reported (0) otherwise.
Q9. Risk of bias criteria	Reported (1) if a tool or criteria are stated, AND if the procedure for assessing risk of bias, AND if the procedure for accounting for the risk of bias in the analysis is stated. If the authors modified existing tools, the modifications are described.
	Not reported (0) otherwise.

Q10. Data synthesis	Reported (1) if the methods for presenting data (e.g., tabular summary, meta-analysis) are stated. If different evidence streams are addressed, a description of how these will be handled (e.g., integrated) is described.
	Not reported (0) otherwise.
Q11. Confidence in cumulative evidence	Reported (1) if an assessment of the certainty of all evidence (e.g., using GRADE) is described.
	Not reported (0) otherwise.

236

237 After extraction, an Excel file with the data was downloaded from Covidence and used
 238 for data analysis.

239 **2.4 Data Analysis**

240 The exported data related to bibliographic information and study characteristics were
 241 summarized using a trend line and bar graphs that were made in GraphPad Prism, and
 242 in tabular format.

243 Due to the complexity of exposures and outcomes collected and to improve data
 244 reporting and facilitate analysis, MPA performed categorization and grouping of these
 245 two characteristics, followed by a second reviewer assessment (SEH). The grouping of
 246 exposures and outcomes was performed in Excel, and the data are available in
 247 Appendix B.4 and B.5 of the Supplementary Material, respectively.

248 Exposure agents were classified as air pollutants, industrial chemicals, pesticides,
 249 metals, pharmaceuticals, cosmetic ingredients, and mycotoxins. For example, all studies
 250 whose exposures fulfilled the World Health Organization (WHO) definition of air pollution
 251 were classified as such (WHO, 2024). Confirmation for the air pollutants category was
 252 performed using the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) Hazardous Airborne
 253 Pollutants (HAPs) list (Agency, 2025). Other distinct categories were established based
 254 on predominant use, regulatory oversight, and classification (e.g., pesticides,
 255 pharmaceuticals, metals, industrial chemicals).

256 Similarly, the outcomes were classified by the target organ system. Where more than
 257 one organ system was assessed, we categorized the outcome as multiple systems.
 258 When the outcome was not specific to the organ system (e.g., genotoxicity or systemic
 259 toxicity), we used the category unspecified. For disease-related outcomes involving

260 multiple organ systems, we used the ICD-11 organ system classification for the disease
261 itself (WHO, 2022).

262 For reporting assessment items, administrative (A1 - A4) and reporting quality-related
263 items (Q1 - Q11) were all used for data visualization. The response options were
264 'reported', coded as '1', and 'not reported', coded as '0', or N/A in case the item is not
265 applicable.

266 The reporting quality of an individual protocol was summarized using the items Q1 to
267 Q11 with an identical binary response format. The reporting quality of an individual
268 protocol is expressed as a percentage of reporting items coded as '1' (q). Assessment of
269 the individual quality items was summarized as the percentage (p) of 'reporting items
270 coded as '1' across all protocols assessed for that item. Detailed formulas are available
271 in the published protocol (Pavlovic et al., 2025). Calculations of q and p are available in
272 Appendix B.7 in Supplementary Material.

273 **2.5 Deviations from the Protocol**

274 Grouping of exposures and outcomes was not previously described in the protocol and
275 was done to facilitate data analysis, as described in 2.4.1. For visualization of reporting
276 quality, we used the traffic light method instead of a histogram. The traffic light was
277 made in Excel and is available in Appendix B.7 of the Supplementary Material. We
278 additionally analyzed whether published protocols provided the PRISMA-P checklist in
279 Appendix B.3 of Supplementary Material (MPA, JM). We did not make a comparison
280 between our reporting assessment and the authors' self-reported PRISMA-P checklist
281 items. This *post-hoc* analysis was briefly discussed in the Results and Discussion
282 section. Due to the limited number of protocols included in this study, observed trends
283 (e.g., correlation between use of checklist and journal) were only briefly discussed in the
284 Discussion and not part of the Results.

285 **3. Results**

286 **3.1 Study Selection**

287 After deduplication ($n = 3,787$), 3,733 records (98.6%) were excluded during title and
288 abstract screening. Fifty-four full texts were assessed, and 17 were excluded based on
289 population, concept, context, or evidence type, resulting in 37 protocols included for

290 analysis. The list of included and excluded records and protocols is available in
291 Appendix B of the Supplementary Material. The study selection process is depicted in
292 the PRISMA flow diagram (Figure 1).

293

294 **Figure 1.** PRISMA flow chart of study selection.

295

296 3.2 Number and yearly distribution of protocols

297 The 37⁸ included protocols were published between 2014 and 2024, i.e., until the date
298 of the search. An increasing trend in the number of published protocols per year was
299 observed until 2021, after which the yearly numbers dropped (Figure 2A). *Environment*
300 *International* published the most protocols (11 / 37), followed by *BMJ Open* (7 / 37) and
301 *Systematic Reviews* (4 / 37). Ten journals published three or fewer eligible protocols
302 each (Figure 2B).

303

304 **Figure 2.** Protocols published per year (A) and number of protocols per journal (B).

305 3.3 Characteristics of included protocols

306 Our second objective was to characterize the protocols in terms of bibliographical data,
307 evidence types, field of study, and guidelines/checklists used. Regionally, most protocols
308 came from Europe, 41% (15 / 37). Country-specific data showed that most protocols
309 originated from China, 16% (6 / 37), followed by the United States, 11% (4 / 37).

310 Overall characteristics of the included protocols are summarized in Table 2. The first
311 authors of 28 of the 37 protocols were affiliated with academia, while the others were
312 affiliated with governments, international organizations (e.g., WHO), or industry. Our
313 data also shows that the topics covered by SRP are mostly related to the field of
314 environmental toxicology, 65% (24 / 37). Seven protocols addressed an occupational
315 toxicology topic, 19% (7 / 37), and interestingly, six protocols considered both exposure

316 scenarios. The majority of protocols, 78% (29/37) were focused on human studies; two
 317 were using only animal studies as the evidence source, and six were deriving their
 318 conclusions from at least two different sources, including human-related studies, animal
 319 studies, and/or new approach methodologies (NAMs).

320 Looking at the exposures intended to be investigated, we found that most studies
 321 focused on the association between air pollution and health outcomes, with the majority
 322 examining ambient (outdoor) air pollutants, 70% (9 / 13). Persistent organic pollutants
 323 (as defined by the Stockholm Convention) were the most investigated industrial
 324 chemicals, 71% (5 / 7), followed by plasticizers like bisphenol-A, and aromatic amines
 325 such as benzidine and beta-naphthylamine. Pesticides ~~were a common focus,~~
 326 ~~appeared~~ appearing in four studies, while three studies addressed heavy metals.

327 Our analysis showed that a broad range of outcomes was addressed. Most studied
 328 outcomes were related to the nervous and respiratory system, 19% (7 / 37 each).
 329 Endpoints related to the female reproductive system, 16% (6 / 37), were significantly
 330 more represented compared to the male reproductive system, 3% (1 / 37). An equal
 331 number of protocols assessed the effects of exposure to pregnancy-related outcomes
 332 involving embryo/fetus 8% (3 / 37), and diseases such as endometriosis and polycystic
 333 ovarian syndrome (PCOS) 8% (3 / 37). The endocrine system, primarily in the context of
 334 metabolic disorders, accounted for 11% of outcomes, followed by the cardiovascular,
 335 hematopoietic, and renal systems.

336 Thirty studies explicitly stated the use of a reporting checklist/guideline for protocol
 337 reporting. The majority mentioned PRISMA-P (70% (26 / 37)), while the remaining three
 338 referred to Recommendations for the conduct of systematic reviews in toxicology and
 339 environmental health research (-COSTER) or RepOrting standards for Systematic
 340 Evidence Syntheses (ROSES). We further analyzed whether PRISMA-P was available
 341 in the Supplementary Material, and in only 38% (14/37) cases was it accompanied by
 342 the document.

343 **Table 3.** *Characteristics of included studies.*

Characteristics	Type	Percentage (Number of protocols / total number)
Field of Study	Environmental	65% (24 / 37)

	Occupational	19% (7 / 37)
	Both	16% (6 / 37)
First author's affiliation	Academia	76% (28 / 37)
	Government	11% (4 / 37)
	Other (non-profit, international organization)	11% (4 / 37)
	Industry	3% (1 / 37)
	Other (non-profit, international organization)	11% (4 / 37)
Type of evidence streams	Human	78% (29 / 37)
	Multiple	16% (6 / 37)
	Animal	5% (2 / 37)
	Multiple	16% (6 / 37)
Exposures	Air pollutants	38% (14 / 37)
	Industrial chemicals	19% (7 / 37)
	Pesticides	11% (4 / 37)
	Metals	8% (3 / 37)
	Pharmaceuticals	8% (3 / 37)
	Others (cosmetics, mycotoxins)	5% (2 / 37)
	Unspecified	5% (2 / 37)
	Multiple	5% (2 / 37)
Outcomes per Organ System	Nervous	19% (7 / 37)
	Respiratory	19% (7 / 37)
	Reproductive, female	16% (6 / 37)
	Multiple	16% (6 / 37)
	Endocrine	11% (4 / 37)
	Others (cardiovascular,	8% (3 / 37)

	circulatory, renal	
	Unspecified	8% (3 / 37)
	Reproductive, male	3% (1 / 37)
	Endocrine	11% (4 / 37)
	Others (cardiovascular, circulatory, renal)	8% (3 / 37)
	Unspecified	8% (3 / 37)
	Multiple	16% (6 / 37)
Guideline/Checklist	PRISMA-P 2015	70% (26 / 37)
	Not reported	22% (8 / 37)
	Other	5% (2 / 37)
	Combined	3% (1 / 37)
	Not reported	22% (8 / 37)

344

345 **3.4 Completeness of reporting**

346 We assessed the included protocols using 15 criteria, including 4 administrative (A1 -
 347 A4) and 11 quality-related (Q1 - Q11) criteria. Results of the assessment of reporting
 348 completeness are summarized in Figure 3.

349 In all 37 assessed protocols, authors reported the funder/sponsor, but in only 30% (11 / 37) of
 350 cases, had they reported the role of the funder/sponsor. For 81% (30 / 37) of the peer-reviewed
 351 protocols published in journals, registration information was also recorded in an external
 352 database, usually PROSPERO.

353 ~~In all 37 assessed protocols, authors reported the funder/sponsor, but in only~~
 354 ~~30% (11 / 37) of cases, had they reported the role of the funder/sponsor. For~~
 355 ~~81% (30 / 37) of the protocols, registration information was recorded in an~~
 356 ~~external database, usually PROSPERO.~~ Authors' contributions were described in
 357 89% (33 / 37) of protocols.

358 When it comes to reporting quality criteria, 32% (12 / 37) of the assessed protocols met
 359 all 11 quality criteria, at least at the minimum level captured by PRISMA-P items used.

360 Twenty-seven percent (10 / 37) failed one criterion, in most cases, the criterion 'Data
361 management procedures' due to a lack of software reporting. Nineteen percent (7 / 37)
362 met nine criteria. This means that 78% (29 / 37) of the protocols met more than 81% (≥ 9
363 / 11) of the reporting quality criteria. Commonly omitted items were the data
364 management and collection procedures, and confidence in cumulative evidence. A
365 similar trend was observed in those that met quality criteria for 6 or fewer items, 11% (4 /
366 37). Of the eight protocols meeting 8 or fewer criteria, at least half did not state the
367 objective, did not fully address data management and data collection procedures, and
368 omitted RoB assessment and confidence in cumulative evidence.

369 In relation to reporting quality items, data management procedures 54% (20 / 37), such
370 as software/platforms used for selection, extraction, and analysis, were the most poorly
371 reported items. This was followed by poor reporting in the assessment of 'confidence in
372 cumulative evidence', 73% (27 / 37), and 'data collection and extraction process', which
373 refers to the number of reviewers, conflict resolution, and extraction, 76% (28 / 37).
374 Assessment of 'risk of bias criteria' was adequately reported in 86% (32 / 37) of
375 protocols, and 'eligibility criteria' and 'research objectives' in 89% (33 / 37). 'Search
376 strategy' that includes search strings was reported in 92% (34 / 37) of protocols. The
377 'selection process', which includes the number of reviewers and conflict resolution, was
378 reported in 95% (35 / 37) of protocols. 'Rationale for the study' and 'data synthesis
379 procedures' were described in 97% (36 / 37) of the protocols. The 'sources of
380 information' were provided in all the examined protocols.

Study ID	Registration	Author contributions	Funder and/or sponsor information	Role of funder and/or sponsor	Rationale	Objectives	Eligibility criteria	Information sources	Search strategy	Data management	Data collection and extraction process	Risk of bias criteria	Data synthesis	Confidence in cumulative evidence	Reporting quality of individual protocol (q)
Tomioka 2014	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	82
Vaccari 2017	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	82
Hall 2017	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	73
Mandrioli 2018	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	100
vanLuijk 2019	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	91
Matta 2019	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	91
Hansen 2019	●	●	●	○	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	91
Tobias 2019	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	82
Zhang 2019	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	55
Li 2019	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	45
Pega 2020	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	100
Nyadanu 2020	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	100
Lux 2020	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	91
Dimala 2020	●	●	●	○	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	82
Zhang 2021	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	100
Uter 2021	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	100
Theron 2021	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	91
CahuanaPinto 2021	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	91
Zhu 2021	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	82
Hamroun 2021	●	●	●	○	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	73
Gamad 2021	●	●	●	○	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	55
Abolghasemi 2021	●	●	●	○	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	45
Shaffer 2022	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	100
Khreis 2022	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	100
Axelrad 2022	●	●	●	○	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	100
Sarah 2022	●	●	●	○	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	91
Linzalone 2022	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	91
Rana 2022	●	●	●	○	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	82
Cao 2022	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	91
RamadhanMakame 2020	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	100
Abbah 2023	●	●	●	○	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	100
Jiang 2023	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	91
Struijs 2023	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	73
Munir 2024	●	●	●	○	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	100
Bline 2024	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	100
Goessens 2024	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	91
Rosendo 2024	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	64
Reporting quality of individual item (p)					97	89	89	100	92	51	95	73	86	97	70

381

382 **Figure 3.** Traffic-light plot of the assessment results for 37 published protocols across 25
383 criteria. Scores: Reported (●), not reported (●), not applicable (○). The overall
384 reporting quality of individual protocols (q) and individual items (p) is expressed as
385 percentages (%). Light blue columns represent administrative items, while quality items
386 are indicated in light yellow columns and included in reporting completeness scores.

387 **4. Discussion**

388 Between 2014 and 2024, a limited number (37) of eligible, peer-reviewed SRPs were
389 identified in our study. Publication rates increased until 2021 before declining, with
390 protocols concentrated in a small number of journals, particularly Environment
391 International, suggesting that editorial policies may strongly influence protocol
392 publication practices in environmental health (Whaley et al., 2016). Most protocols were
393 published by authors from academia and focused on environmental toxicology, with air
394 pollution as the most common exposure and human health evidence as the dominant
395 evidence base. Overall reporting quality was relatively high when assessed against the
396 adapted PRISMA-P 2015 reporting checklist, with 32% of SRPs meeting all required
397 reporting items. Of all administrative items assessed, role of funder was the most under-
398 reported (30% (11 / 37). Data management procedures, data extraction processes, and
399 assessment of confidence in cumulative evidence remained poorly reported, indicating
400 that adherence to reporting guidelines does not necessarily ensure complete
401 transparency in key methodological domains.

402 Our findings highlight important issues related to reporting practices and the
403 implementation of methodological standards.

404 The thematic and methodological profiles of protocols indicate that SR activity in
405 toxicology is largely driven by established evidence bases and regulatory relevance
406 (Farhat et al., 2022; Wikoff & Fitch, 2024). The predominance of human health-oriented
407 evidence synthesis, alongside limited incorporation of animal studies and human-based,
408 new approach methodologies (NAMs), suggests that newer or less standardized
409 evidence streams have not yet been fully integrated into systematic evidence synthesis
410 practice (Hooijmans et al., 2018; Krebs et al., 2025; National Academies of Sciences et
411 al., 2023; van der Zalm et al., 2022). The few animal studies were mostly for the purpose
412 of setting occupational exposure limits (Struijs et al., 2023; van Luijk et al., 2019). Only
413 four protocols included evidence from NAMs (Matta et al., 2021; Ramadhan Makame et
414 al., 2023; Uter et al., 2021; Vaccari et al., 2017). The strong focus on air pollution further
415 reflects the maturity of this field, where long-standing epidemiological evidence and
416 policy relevance have enabled sustained use of SRs in decision-making contexts
417 (Forastiere, 2024; Forastiere et al., 2024; Fowler et al., 2020; WHO, 2024). These
418 patterns likely reflect broader structural features of toxicological evidence generation,
419 where research priorities are shaped by public health relevance, regulatory demand, and

420 the availability of funding for primary research (Haby et al., 2025; Norris et al., 2021;
421 Wikoff et al., 2020). In turn, the existence of a robust primary evidence base facilitates
422 further synthesis activity, reinforcing a feedback loop between policy needs, research
423 funding, and evidence generation (Chartres et al., 2025; Hoffmann et al., 2017; Sesin et
424 al., 2023). This dynamic helps explain why SRs cluster in certain exposure domains
425 while remaining limited in emerging or less-established methodological areas.

426 Although most protocols reported using PRISMA-P (70%, 26 / 37) this did not
427 consistently translate into more complete reporting, with some of the lowest-scoring
428 protocols stating adherence to the reporting checklist. Furthermore, only 38% (14 / 37) of
429 those reporting use of PRISMA-P provided the checklist in Supplementary materials.
430 This lack of association between checklist use and reporting completeness suggests a
431 persistent gap between formal endorsement and its practical implementation (Kusala
432 Pussegoda et al., 2017). The dominance of PRISMA-P, which was designed for health
433 and medical studies in general, may stem from the absence of toxicology-specific
434 guidance, as well as its widespread adoption, large user base, and endorsement by
435 journals (Page et al., 2021; Pearson et al., 2025). Interestingly, we observed
436 inconsistencies within the same journal (e.g., BMJ Open), with some publications using
437 reporting checklists while others did not (Sarah et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2021)
438 suggesting a lack of uniform editorial practices. Consistent with our findings, the
439 ASPIRE-SCAGE and ASPIRE-UK studies reported modest improvements in adherence
440 to SPIRIT recommendations over time, although reporting remained incomplete overall
441 and important gaps persisted, particularly in investigator- or non-industry-sponsored
442 clinical trial protocols (Gryaznov et al., 2022; Speich et al., 2022). Together, these
443 findings indicate that improving reporting quality requires not only guideline
444 dissemination but also stronger editorial and reviewer enforcement mechanisms
445 (Schlussel et al., 2023).

446 Despite overall high completeness of reporting, important gaps remain in core domains
447 of transparency, such as funding roles, data management procedures, data extraction
448 processes and assessment of certainty in the evidence base. These omissions are
449 important because they limit the interpretability and reproducibility of systematic review
450 protocols and may weaken confidence in subsequent evidence synthesis (Du et al.,
451 2022; Schlussel et al., 2023).

452 Underreporting of funding roles is particularly relevant given evidence that funding
453 structures can influence study design and interpretation in ways that affect research
454 conclusions, as seen in the examples derived from pharmaceutical and food industry
455 (Bes-Rastrollo et al., 2013; Carducci et al., 2018; Rosenberg et al., 2013; Ross et al.,
456 2008).

457 'Data management procedures' (Q6) that included indicating the software used across
458 different study stages were incompletely reported in 54% (20 / 37) of cases. In 76% (28 /
459 37) of cases, the authors did not describe the 'Data extraction' (Q8) procedure in enough
460 detail. This could be partially explained by our assessment approach, where these two
461 items required three conditions to be reported, making it more sensitive to reveal under-
462 reporting.

463 In our study, 70% of SRs reported confidence in cumulative evidence assessment and
464 interestingly it was reported in all SRs that included more than two evidence streams.
465 Certainty/confidence of evidence (CoE, formerly quality of evidence) assessment is a
466 fundamental component of SRs because it evaluates the overall confidence that can be
467 placed in a body of evidence by considering domains such as risk of bias, consistency,
468 directness, precision (Brignardello-Petersen & Guyatt, 2025). Frameworks commonly
469 applied include GRADE, and its adaptations in the field of environmental health: the
470 Office of Health Assessment and Translation (OHAT) approach, and the Navigation
471 Guide (Prasad, 2024; Radke et al., 2026; Rooney et al., 2014; Woodruff & Sutton, 2014).
472 The extensive effort of GRADE Working Group in the field of public and environmental
473 health is summarized elsewhere (Morgan et al., 2019). Transparent reporting of CoE
474 assessment requires clear documentation of the framework used, the domains
475 evaluated, the rationale for each judgment, and the resulting certainty ratings for
476 individual outcomes (Prasad, 2024; Shaheen et al., 2023; Siedler et al., 2024).
477 Underreporting of this process reduces the transparency, reproducibility, and
478 trustworthiness of systematic reviews by obscuring the basis for confidence in the
479 findings and limiting the ability of regulators, policymakers, and other stakeholders to
480 appropriately interpret and apply the evidence in risk assessment and decision-making
481 contexts (Brignardello-Petersen & Guyatt, 2025; Siedler et al., 2024).

482 Overall, these issues appear consistent with patterns observed across other fields of
483 evidence synthesis (Frost et al., 2022; Innocenti et al., 2022; Ivaldi et al., 2024; Panic et
484 al., 2013). The role of funder/sponsor information, confidence in cumulative evidence,

485 and risk of bias were also the items poorly reported for published PubMed-indexed
486 protocols in the study by Frost et al., showing concordance with our results and a pattern
487 present across disciplines, at least in the domain of peer-reviewed literature (Frost et al.,
488 2022).

489 In summary, due to the nature of SRs, most of them cover exposures with a long history
490 of research and outcomes with important public health relevance. Most protocols
491 reported using the PRISMA-P 2015 checklist and adhered to the minimum reporting
492 requirements. However, it seems that there remains considerable room for improvement
493 in relation to how SRPs in toxicology are reported, especially regarding the reporting of
494 'data management procedures' and 'confidence in cumulative evidence'. Although the
495 overall reporting quality of SRPs assessed in this study could be considered good,
496 follow-up studies investigating the appropriateness of how items were addressed and
497 the adherence of SRs to published SRPs are needed; such protocol-paper comparisons
498 have been performed in other fields, for systematic reviews with PROSPERO protocols
499 and published protocols (Hopewell et al., 2002; Hu et al., 2021; Koensgen et al., 2019;
500 Siebert et al., 2023). Importantly, reporting completeness should not be equated with
501 methodological rigor (Faggion Jr, 2023). A protocol may comprehensively report
502 suboptimal or inappropriate methods, while a methodologically robust protocol may
503 nevertheless omit important reporting details (Faggion Jr, 2023; K. Pussegoda et al.,
504 2017). Accordingly, our findings should be interpreted as an assessment of transparency
505 rather than methodological validity. Importantly, reporting completeness should not be
506 equated with methodological rigor.

507 This work provides a foundation for future research and highlights several important
508 avenues for further investigation. Future studies should assess the impact of protocol
509 development and preregistration on the methodological rigor of SRs in environmental
510 health, for example by comparing the methodological quality of reviews with registered
511 or published protocols to those conducted without a protocol. Additionally, comparing the
512 quality of protocols published in registries with those published in peer-reviewed journals
513 would help determine the added value of peer review in improving protocol quality. Our
514 meta-epidemiology study showed a nonlinear trend in the number of published protocols
515 over time, in line with previously published data suggesting a low number of these types
516 of publications in clinical fields (Van Der Braak et al., 2023). Most protocols were
517 published by authors who work in academia rather than government or industry.

518 However, it is important to note that our study focuses solely on peer-reviewed protocols
519 published in scientific journals, excluding those found in grey literature, which may be
520 the preferred repository in other sectors. The leading role of *Environment International*
521 can be explained by the journal's introduction of reporting standards, editorial processes,
522 and an associate editor for systematic reviews in 2016 (Whaley et al., 2016).

523 Most protocols included evidence from human studies. The few animal studies were
524 mostly for the purpose of setting occupational exposure limits (Struijs et al., 2023; van
525 Luijk et al., 2019). Only four protocols included evidence from NAMs (Matta et al., 2021;
526 Ramadhan Makame et al., 2023; Uter et al., 2021; Vaccari et al., 2017). Protocols
527 aiming to examine the association between air pollution exposure and health effects
528 were most frequent, in 38% (14 / 37) of cases. Air pollution stands out among
529 environmental exposures due to its robust epidemiological data, strong causal inference,
530 and the established use of systematic reviews in regulatory decisions (Forastiere, 2024;
531 Forastiere et al., 2024; Fowler et al., 2020). Respiratory and nervous, followed by the
532 female reproductive system, were the health outcomes most frequently addressed in
533 included protocols.

534 This data could be explained by the fact that in toxicology, performing SR is typically
535 driven by factors such as the public health relevance of the topic and the associated
536 policy and regulatory needs (Hoffmann et al., 2017). These needs, in turn, influence
537 research funding opportunities, which are crucial for generating a robust body of primary
538 research (Sesin et al., 2023). This body of evidence is both essential for and reliant upon
539 evidence synthesis to support informed decision-making (Sesin et al., 2023).

540 The statement on the use of the reporting checklist/guideline was high, with 70% (26 /
541 37) relying on PRISMA-P (Shamseer et al., 2015). Further evaluation revealed that 38%
542 (14 / 37) provided PRISMA-P in the Supplementary Material. The dominance of
543 PRISMA-P, which was designed for health and medical studies in general, may stem
544 from the absence of toxicology-specific guidance, as well as its widespread adoption,
545 large user base, and endorsement by journals. This suggests that authors of peer-
546 reviewed protocols recognize the value of standardized reporting checklists.
547 Interestingly, we observed inconsistencies within the same journal (e.g., *BMJ Open*),
548 with some publications using reporting checklists while others did not, suggesting a lack
549 of uniform editorial practices even within the same year.

550 We found no clear link between using the checklist and how many items were
551 reported. Even some of the lowest scoring protocols did state adherence to the
552 reporting checklist. This suggests that just an explicit statement of using the
553 checklist or guideline does not necessarily mean the authors would adhere to it,
554 nor are reviewers assessing compliance with it, as suggested by previous authors
555 (Pussegoda et al., 2017).

556 Although the majority of SRP self-reported using the PRISMA P 2015 checklist, we
557 further assessed the presence of reporting individual items per paper and cumulatively.
558 The role of funder/sponsor was the most frequently omitted item, in 32% (12/37) of
559 protocols, irrespective of the authors' affiliation. Previous studies addressing the quality
560 of reporting in different fields showed a similar trend of underreporting of the
561 funder/sponsor information; however, without stratifying it to the level of the sponsor role
562 (Buitrago-Garcia et al., 2024). Reporting of the funder/sponsor and their role in different
563 aspects of the publication process, from publication planning to access to provisional
564 data, is important to avoid the sponsor's misconduct or engagement in unethical
565 practices, such as ghost authorship (Rosenberg et al., 2013). Empirical analyses of
566 cases such as manufacturer-sponsored trials of rofecoxib, industry-supported reviews
567 that downplayed the role of dietary sugars in cardiovascular disease, and beverage
568 industry-funded studies reporting neutral effects of sugar-sweetened beverages illustrate
569 how study design, outcome selection, and reporting practices can systematically
570 advantage sponsor interests (Bes-Rastrollo et al., 2013; Kearns et al., 2016; Ross et al.,
571 2008). These patterns underscore the need for transparency in funding disclosures,
572 independent data access, and better assessment of methodological choices in
573 commercially funded research.

574 'Data management procedures' (Q6) that included indicating the software used across
575 different study stages were incompletely reported in 54% (20 / 37) of cases. In 76% (28 /
576 37) of cases, the authors did not describe the 'Data extraction' (Q8) procedure in enough
577 detail. This could be partially explained by our assessment approach, where these two
578 items required three conditions to be reported, making it more sensitive to reveal under-
579 reporting. The authors did not address how confidence in the body of evidence will be
580 assessed (e.g., by using GRADE) in 30% (11 / 37) of cases. Lack of understanding,
581 such as unawareness of toxicology-specific risk of bias and evidence integration tools,
582 might be the cause behind this issue (Hartung & Tsaioun, 2024). Interestingly, 16% (6 /

583 ~~37) that included more than two evidence streams also reported 'confidence in~~
584 ~~cumulative evidence' analysis, but with no evidence-specific methodology.~~

585 ~~The role of funder/sponsor information, confidence in cumulative evidence, and risk of~~
586 ~~bias were also the items poorly reported for published protocols in the study by Frost et~~
587 ~~al., showing concordance with our results and a pattern present across disciplines, at~~
588 ~~least in the domain of peer-reviewed literature (Frost et al., 2022). Similar trends are also~~
589 ~~observed in the reporting of completed systematic reviews and meta-analyses (Innocenti~~
590 ~~et al., 2022; Ivaldi et al., 2024; Panic et al., 2013).~~

591 ~~In summary, due to the nature of SR, most of them cover exposures with a long history~~
592 ~~of research and outcomes with important public health relevance. Most of the studies~~
593 ~~reported the use of the PRISMA-P 2015 reporting checklist and adhered to the minimum~~
594 ~~reporting requirements. However, it seems that there is space for improvement in~~
595 ~~relation to how SRPs in toxicology are reported, especially regarding the reporting of~~
596 ~~'data management procedures' and 'confidence in cumulative evidence'. Although the~~
597 ~~overall reporting quality of SRP assessed in this study could be considered good, follow-~~
598 ~~up studies investigating the appropriateness of how items were addressed and the~~
599 ~~adherence of SR to published protocols are needed; such protocols papers comparisons~~
600 ~~have been performed in other fields, for systematic reviews with PROSPERO protocols~~
601 ~~and published protocols (Silgagy et al., 2002; Koensgen et al., 2019, Hu et al., 2021;~~
602 ~~Siebert et al., 2023). This work also opens doors for further studies assessing the impact~~
603 ~~of preregistration/protocols on systematic review rigour in environmental health (for~~
604 ~~instance by comparing methodological rigour between systematic review, which had a~~
605 ~~protocol, vs systematic review without a registered protocol.~~

606 **Limitations**

607 We are aware that a small number of protocols meeting the inclusion criteria (37) limits
608 our ability to statistically assess the trends. However, we also consider this a finding –
609 that publishing SRPs, in the case of environmental and occupational exposures, in peer-
610 reviewed journals is not widespread among researchers in this field. Also, our approach
611 of checking if certain reporting items were present, but not if they were implemented
612 appropriately, limits the assessment of the quality of the SRPs. While not meeting
613 several of our assessment criteria is a clear indication of low reporting quality, meeting
614 all criteria does not necessarily mean that the protocol is of high quality. For example,

615 describing how RoB was assessed does not imply that a suitable tool for the
616 assessment was chosen, or providing a search string does not mean that the search
617 string does not contain errors or is sensitive enough to retrieve most of the relevant
618 evidence. ~~Finally, Our~~ assessment criteria represent minimal reporting requirements,
619 rather than requirements for comprehensive reporting of all relevant methodological
620 details. For example, we scored the search strategy as present if the search string for at
621 least one database is provided, but ideally, complete search strings should be provided
622 for all used databases, and they should be benchmarked for retrieval sensitivity via
623 relative recall (Lagisz et al., 2025). [Finally, this assessment is relevant at the protocol
624 level but provides limited information lack informativeness on quality at the final
625 publication level; a well reported protocol does not equate to a rigorous or well reported
626 systematic review. Further studies on this topic are warranted, as mentioned in the
627 section above.](#)

628 **5. Conclusions**

629 Overall, our meta-epidemiology study shows a low number of peer-reviewed protocols
630 published in scientific journals in the field of toxicology. Although the minimum reporting
631 quality was acceptable, improvement in [reporting](#) data management, funders/sponsor
632 involvement, and confidence in cumulative evidence could be improved. Further
633 research is needed to assess the quality of protocols in greater detail; to evaluate how
634 closely systematic reviews adhere to their pre-published protocols, [to evaluate if SR with
635 pre-published protocols are 'better' than those without,](#) and to expand the assessment to
636 SRP published in grey literature.

637 **Data and code availability statement**

638 The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in Zenodo, DOI:
639 10.5281/zenodo.18187257.

640 **Contributions**

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653 Supervision: Sebastian Hoffmann and Milica D. Pavlovic.
654 Writing - original draft: Milica D. Pavlovic, Sebastian Hoffmann, and Julia M. L. Menon.
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656 M. L. Menon, Gunn E. Vist, Elma Omeragic, and Rebecca L. Morgan, Sebastian
657 Hoffmann.

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660 **Disclosure statement**

661 The authors report there are no competing interests to declare.

662 **Supplementary Material:**

663 **Appendix A - Reporting checklists**

- 664 ● A.1 - PRISMA - A (2020)
- 665 ● A.2 - PRISMA - S (2020)
- 666 ● A.3 - Adapted PRISMA (2017) checklist for meta-epidemiology study

667 **Appendix B**

- 668 ● B.1 - metadata
- 669 ● B.2 - List of Excluded Records
- 670 ● B.3 - List of Included Records
- 671 ● B.4 - Exposure
- 672 ● B.5 - Outcome
- 673 ● B.6 - Quality Assessment
- 674 ● B.7 - Summary of Quality Assessment

675

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681 [DD/appendix-Table%201%20to%20Subpart%20DD%20of%20Part%2063](https://www.ecfr.gov/current/title-40/chapter-I/subchapter-C/part-63/subpart-DD/appendix-Table%201%20to%20Subpart%20DD%20of%20Part%2063)
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